

ANALYSING THE INFLUENCE OF MANUFACTURING COOLING RATE ON THE IMPACT RESPONSE OF CARBON FIBRE/POLYPHENYLENESULFIDE(CF/PPS)

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the influence of cooling rate on the impact response of Carbon Fibre/PolyPhenyleneSulfide (CF/PPS). Numerical simulations are developed which analyse the low-velocity impact response of unidirectional layup configurations. Intralaminar failure is modelled using the Chang-Chang strength-based failure criterion. Interlaminar delamination is modelled using a bilinear cohesive traction-separation law. The impact simulation results are compared with the results of drop-tower impact test results showing qualitative agreement in terms of maximum impact force. The results of this work highlight the importance of cooling rate on impact force and delamination of CF/PPS. Higher cooling rates were shown to increase fracture toughness reducing impact damage and delamination.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic matrix materials have a number of advantages compared to thermosets including low relative cost and processing time, high toughness and recyclability [1]. However, similar to Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (CFRP), Thermoplastic Composite (TPC) materials including those reinforced with Carbon Fibre (CF) are susceptible to impact damage sustained during manufacture and/or in-service [2]. Low-energy and low-velocity impact damage can result in significant damage leading to sub-surface matrix cracking, fibre fracture and delamination. Gao et al. [3] have noted that the mechanical properties and fracture resistance may be optimised by controlling the processing conditions in particular the manufacturing cooling rate. In the case of CF/PEEK (PolyEtherEtherKetone) slow cooling was shown to improve the fibre-matrix interface bond strength and stiffness. Fast cooling increases ductility of the PEEK matrix increasing the interlaminar fracture toughness and impact resistance. Understanding the influence of laminate cooling rate on the impact tolerance of thermoplastic CFRP is important to improve the design of future components. This current study investigates the influence of cooling rate on the impact response of Carbon Fibre/PolyPhenyleneSulfide (CF/PPS). Numerical simulations are developed which analyse the low-velocity impact response of unidirectional layup configurations. Intralaminar failure is modelled using the Chang-Chang strength-based failure criterion. Interlaminar delamination is modelled using a bilinear cohesive traction-separation law.

2 MATERIALS

2.1 Mechanical properties

TenCate Cetex[®] TC1100 PPS resin system was used in conjunction with AS4A Unidirectional (UD) tape with a fibre volume fraction $V_f = 0.59$. The relevant mechanical property data for slow (8 °C/min) and fast cooling rates (150 °C/min inside laminate and 230 °C/min at surface of laminate) are shown in Table 1 [4-5].

Property	Symbol	Slow cool 8 °C/min	Fast cool 150 °C/min
Density	ρ	1.6 g/cm ³	1.6 g/cm ³
Modulus in 1-direction	E_{11}	111.2 GPa	109.6 GPa
Modulus in 2-direction	$E_{22} = E_{33}$	8.7 GPa	7.87 GPa
Shear modulus	$G_{12} = G_{31}$	3.91 GPa	3.73 GPa
Shear modulus	G_{23}	2.92 GPa	2.67 GPa
Major Poisson's ratio	μ_{12}	0.371	0.351
Minor Poisson's ratio	$\mu_{21} = \mu_{31}$	0.029	0.025
Strength in 1-direction tension	S_1	2.02 GPa	2.02 GPa
Strength in 2-direction tension	S_2	39 MPa	39 MPa
Strength in 2-direction compression	C_2	148 MPa	148 MPa
Shear strength	S_{12}	82 MPa	82 MPa

Table 1: Mechanical property data for TenCate Cetex[®] TC1100 PPS/AS4.

Laminates were prepared with a layup sequence $[0^\circ]_{48}$ measuring 100 mm x 100 mm x 7 mm in dimension. The mode I and mode II critical fracture energy values G_{IC} , G_{IIC} were measured from End Notched Flexure (ENF) and Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) tests respectively. In the case of slow cooled laminates the G_{IC} and G_{IIC} values were 202 J/m² and 1014 J/m² respectively. Fast cooled laminates showed higher values of 282 J/m² and 1705 J/m². This increase in fracture energy value is attributed to the change in crystallinity and morphology of the laminate during fast cooling.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Impact testing

Low-velocity impact testing was performed using a IITM-18S-KW, YONEKURA MFG Co. Ltd. test device with a hemi-spherical tup measuring 5/8" (15.875mm) in diameter. The CF/PPS specimens were clamped from the impact side at all four corners and supported by a steel plate with a circular cut-out 75 mm in diameter based on the JIS K7089 reference method [6]. Impact testing was performed at four impact energy values including 1 J, 3 J, 5 J and 7 J based on a drop mass of 5.6 kg.

4 SIMULATION SETUP

A schematic image showing the simulation setup is shown in Fig. 1. The model consisted of four sub-laminates with three layers of cohesive elements to model interlaminar failure. Fixed boundary conditions were applied at the circumference of the laminate.

4.1 Software

The simulations were created using the pre-processing software LS-PrePost 4.1 and solved with LS-DYNA 971 R8.1.0 (64-bit SMP) running on an HP Z840 workstation [7].

Figure 1: Schematic of simulation setup.

4.2 Material models

The TenCate Cetex[®] TC1100 PPS/AS4 coupons were simulated in LS-DYNA using the composite material model *MAT_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE (MAT_22). Intralaminar failure was modelled using the Chang-Chang strength-based failure criterion. The Chang-Chang failure criterion includes the following five material parameters: longitudinal tensile strength (S_1) transverse tensile strength (S_2), shear strength (S_{12}), transverse compressive strength (C_2) and γ the nonlinear shear stress parameter as defined in [7] and reproduced here. S_1 , S_2 , S_{12} and C_2 are determined from material strength measurements while the nonlinear shear parameter γ is defined by shear stress-strain measurements with a value of $\gamma = 0$ resulting in the standard linear-orthotropic Chang-Chang model. In plane stress conditions the strain is related to the stress by the following equations:

$$\varepsilon_1 = \frac{1}{E_1}(\sigma_1 - \mu_{12}\sigma_2), \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_2 = \frac{1}{E_2}(\sigma_2 - \mu_{21}\sigma_1), \quad (2)$$

$$2\varepsilon_{12} = \frac{1}{G_{12}}\tau_{12} + \gamma\tau_{12}^3, \quad (3)$$

where ε is strain, E is Young's modulus, σ is stress, μ is Poisson's ratio, G is the shear modulus and τ is the shear stress. A fibre matrix shearing term is then used to supplement each damage mode:

$$\bar{\tau} = \frac{\frac{\tau_{12}^2}{2G_{12}} + \frac{3}{4}\gamma\tau_{12}^4}{\frac{S_{12}^2}{2G_{12}} + \frac{3}{4}\gamma S_{12}^4}. \quad (4)$$

The failure of the matrix F_m is determined from:

$$F_m = \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{S_2}\right)^2 + \bar{\tau}. \quad (5)$$

In Equation (5) when failure occurs ($F_m > 1$) the material constants E_2 , G_{12} , μ_{12} and μ_{21} are set to zero. In compression the failure criteria is defined as:

$$F_{comp} = \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{2S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{C_2}{2S_{12}}\right)^2 - 1\right]\frac{\sigma_2}{C_2} + \bar{\tau}. \quad (6)$$

In Equation (6) when failure occurs ($F_{comp} > 1$) the material constants E_2 , μ_{12} and μ_{21} are set to zero. The final failure mode due to fibre breakage is defined as:

$$F_f = \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{S_1}\right)^2 + \bar{\tau}. \quad (7)$$

In this case when failure occurs ($F_f > 1$) the material constants $E_1, E_2, G_{12}, \mu_{12}$ and μ_{21} are set to zero. It should be noted that if the index 2 is replaced with 3 in the above criteria then the above rules also apply to failure in the transverse 3 direction and the 1-3 plane.

Figure 2: Schematic of mixed-mode cohesive element traction-separation law.

Interlaminar failure was modelled using a bilinear cohesive material model *MAT_COHESIVE_MIXED_MODE (MAT_138), Fig. 2 which includes a bilinear traction-separation law with quadratic mixed mode delamination criteria and damage formulation [7]. This delamination model has been validated in earlier work involving DCB, ENF and Fixed Ratio Mixed Mode Bending (FRMMB) simulations with UD specimens [8]. The mixed-mode failure displacement is calculated using the following power-law failure criterion:

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}}\right)^\alpha = 1, \quad (8)$$

where G_I and G_{II} are the mode I and mode II strain energy release rates respectively. The parameter α in Equation (8) is an empirical parameter derived from testing. In Fig. 2 T and S are defined as the peak traction in the normal and tangential directions respectively. The total mixed-mode relative displacement is defined as δ_m where δ_I and δ_{II} are the separation in the normal (mode I) and tangential directions (mode II) respectively. The onset of softening is denoted by δ^0 with the ultimate mixed-mode displacement for total failure defined as δ^F . The stiffness normal to the cohesive element K_I and in the plane of the cohesive element K_{II} is defined with the peak traction in the normal $\sigma_{I,max}$ and tangential $\sigma_{II,max}$ directions. The steel projectile was modelled using rigid material model *MAT_RIGID (MAT_20) with a density of 7850 kg/m^3 , Young's modulus of 210 GPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.3.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Impact testing

The maximum impact force for slow and fast cooled laminates are presented in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 respectively. The drop-tower test results show a general trend of increasing impact force with impact energy reaching a maximum impact force of approximately 6 kN at 7 J.

5.2 Simulations

The simulation results for maximum impact force in slow and fast cooled laminates are compared to the results of experiments in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. In the case of slow cooled laminates the simulation results show a similar trend to the experiment results of increasing maximum impact force with impact energy. The simulation results are shown to have a higher maximum impact force when compared to the experiments reaching a maximum of 26% at 3J.

Figure 3: Maximum impact force as a function of impact energy for slow cooled laminates.

Figure 4: Maximum impact force as a function of impact energy for fast cooled laminates.

At 7 J the difference between the simulation and experiment result was approximately 1.2%. Similar to the results of experiments and simulations based on slow cooled laminates the maximum impact force in the fast cooled simulations was shown to increase with increasing impact energy. The maximum impact force was also higher when compared to the experiments reaching a maximum of 29.5% at 5 J and a minimum of 6.9% at 7 J. The simulation results for fast cooled laminates showed a higher maximum impact force than slow cooled laminates which is attributed to the difference in effective stiffness, fracture energy and extent of delamination.

Simulation results showing the extent of interlaminar delamination for slow and fast cooled laminates are presented in Fig. 5. Delamination was not predicted in either slow or fast cooled laminates at the lowest impact energy 1 J. Small peanut shaped delaminations in the direction of the $[0^\circ]$ plies were first predicted in the slow cooled laminate at 3 J although no delamination was predicted in the fast cooled case. Delamination was then predicted at 5 J and 7 J in both the slow and fast cooled laminates also in the direction of the $[0^\circ]$ plies.

Figure 5: Simulation results showing interlaminar delamination (grey) of lowest sub-laminate in slow and fast cooled specimens as a function of impact energy.

In all cases with delamination the fast cooled laminates showed a lower delamination area than the equivalent slow cooled laminates. The lack of delamination at 3 J in the fast cooled case and the smaller area of delamination when compared to the slow cooled laminates at 5 J and 7 J was attributed to the faster cooling rate and the associated higher fracture energy.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigates the influence of cooling rate on the impact response of Carbon Fibre/PolyPhenyleneSulfide (CF/PPS). Numerical simulations were developed which analyse the low-velocity impact response of slow cooled and fast cooled unidirectional layup configurations. Intralaminar failure was modelled using the Chang-Chang strength-based failure criterion. Interlaminar delamination was modelled using a bilinear cohesive traction-separation law. The impact simulation results were compared with the results of drop-tower impact test results showing qualitative agreement in terms of maximum impact force. Impact force was shown to increase with increasing impact energy for slow and fast cooled laminates. The simulation results of interlaminar delamination showed a general increase in delamination area with impact energy. Fast cooled laminates were shown to have a lower delamination extent when compared to slow cooled laminates attributed to the faster cooling rate and the associated higher fracture energy. The results of this work highlight the importance of cooling rate on fracture energy and its potential role in controlling the intralaminar failure and interlaminar delamination of CF/PPS.

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